

Metro Dwelling rate Prediction using Regression Optimization

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ABSTRACT

‘Dwelling’ means where the people used to stay (houses). The common people dream is to own a comfortable house at affordable price in cities now. The price variations are becoming a great challenge to make a customer to buy a house at right time with right price. Many negotiations on prices due to the broker’s involvement make customers unpredictable about house prices in the market. Our work mainly focuses over application of machine learning algorithm on available training data to predict accurate house prices in real time. Even though regression model applied by earlier researchers in this problem domain we focused to improve the accuracy using random forests and some metrics in our paper.

Keywords: - *Random Forests, Linear Regression, Confusion matrix, Precision measures.*

1. INTRODUCTION

House price prediction strongly influenced by correlated factors like location, area, government regulations and population in a territory [5]. Machine learning algorithms like Linear Regression, Random Forest are widely used by many researchers to analyze the statistical data. To optimize the growth of random forest only highly influenced variables considered for prediction algorithms [4]. The application of Random forests and Gradient Boosting algorithms effectively captures correlation factors between class features and target values which improves prediction accuracy [3]. The increased migration of citizens from rural to urban areas is increasing the demand for houses in cities, causing prices to hike [7]. K-mean algorithm used by some researchers to cluster the zones based on various criteria provides an insight into various dimensions of price predictions [8]. Many performance metrics available to apply over classification and regression models to identify most accurate

prediction technique forgiven training data [2][3]. Real estate market exhibits historical trends which have ups and downs. Market trends are useful data to predict future value of properties by analyzing patterns of house rates [9][1]. In this paper we applied various ML algorithms and compared their accuracy in prediction with some metrics. We highlighted the combination of regression and tree models in performance improvement in prediction [10].

2. DATA PROCESSING

The data set collection obtained from online ‘KAGLE’ data repository in the .CSV file format. The data preprocessing conducted over data based on local preferences of house pricing. The various data refinement techniques applied before data processing is missing value filling (Average/Mean/Mode - based), Null value substitutions, smoothing and binning. Once the aggregated data prepared it is considered as training – data for our work. The data pre – process pipeline is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Data Pre-processing pipeline

The features extracted are the selected columns which are having high information gain during classification.

3. METHODOLOGY

Pre-Processing:

The data collected from open resource need to be standardized, using sklearn package in python

we apply StandardScaler method over data. This scales data by removing mean and maintain unit variance. This is a common requirement for many machine learning estimator algorithms. To apply linear regression we need to perform column transformation where it fits multiple transformations to multiple columns with single fit function. We use ColumnTransformer method from sklearn package in python for this work. Now we need to eliminate missing values and noise from the data. For this we use SimpleImputer class in sklearn library. It applies collection of strategies to replace missing values (NaNs) with specified values computed with mean, mode, median or constant.

Sequencing Process:

To enhance the predictive model behavior, pipeline class used in this work from sklearn. It provides sequential list of transformers applied over data for concluding predictors with best fit criteria.

Modeling Labels:

The train_test_split function used at this stage to split a dataset into training and testing subsets. This process is crucial in machine learning to evaluate the performance of a model on unseen data. The function returns X_train (feature train data) and X_test (feature testing data) Y_train (Target train data) and Y_test (Target test data).

Random Forest Regression:

A random forest is a Meta estimator that fits a number of decision tree regressors on various sub-samples of the dataset and uses averaging to improve the predictive accuracy and control over-fitting. The function used to measure the quality of a split. Supported criteria are "Squared_Error" for the mean squared error, which is equal to variance reduction as feature selection criterion and minimizes the L2 loss using the mean of each terminal node. The "Friedman_MSE", which uses mean squared error with Friedman's improvement score for potential splits, "Absolute_Error" for the mean absolute error, which minimizes the L1 loss using the median of each terminal node, and

"Poisson" which uses reduction in Poisson deviance to find splits. Training using "Absolute_Error" is significantly slower than when using "Squared_Error".

Finally we turned all the best features obtained from random forest classification into coefficients for Linear Regression based prediction.

4. RESULT ANALYSIS

In our work Random Forest with XG-Boost and Gradient Boost approaches applied over data. The classification patterns are visualized using Heat-Map (Figure 2) technique highly useful to insight the prediction data patterns with classifier rates.

Figure 2: Heat Map of House Price Prediction

The linear regression model applied over data sets identifies relationships between label sets. The correlation and coupling factors are exactly identified by using this method. The 'Best-Fit' criteria identifies the future data sets position in existed classes, also maximizes the predicted actual values. As shown in Figure 3 shows the various ranges in house prices predicted among amount of houses available in locations. The results will identify various patterns of customer buying interest based house price values.

Figure 3: Regression Model of HRP

Figure 4: Confusion Matrix of HRP classification

We examined the classification accuracy by using confusion matrix model. This visualization shows actual classes and predicted classes with true positive and true negative instances classified. The model also shows the misclassified instances of each algorithm applied. The proposed ensemble approach shows good performance among other machine learning algorithms.

Table 1: Classification Metrics

	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
High	0.76	0.58	0.66	43
Low	0.90	0.93	0.91	34
Medium	0.79	0.88	0.83	35
Very High	0.76	0.80	0.78	55
Very Low	0.84	0.58	0.69	86
Accuracy	0.86	0.75	0.85	85
Macro Avg.	0.81	0.85	0.77	87
Weighted Avg.	0.85	0.58	0.85	43

The classification metrics are compared among Random Forest, Linear Regression, SVM (Support Vector Machine) and Decision Tree. The proposed approach with XG-Boost and

Gradient Boost applied Random Forest shown great accuracy and improved classification metrics value. We obtained an accuracy and precision between 0.85 – 0.90 which is an improvement compared to application of independent classification algorithms.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper we applied a combination of Machine Learning algorithms to classify the house rates in metro cities. The application of random forests with boosting algorithms improved the classification rate. The comparison of various classification algorithms with proposed approach proved a great performance improvement. In future with growth of urbanization the demand of house actual price prediction is becoming a challenge. Since application of AI algorithms is our next direction to identify a solution with great optimization.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Maloku, Besnik Maloku, A. Agarwal, "House Price Prediction Using Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence", *Journal of Artificial Intelligence and Cloud Computing*, Vol.3, PP: 1-10, 2024.
- [2] J. Kalidas, R. Nivetha, "House Price Prediction using Machine Learning", *IRJET*, vol.11, Issue-4, PP:1351-1358, ISSN: 2395 - 0072, 2024.
- [3] Margot Greets, S.V. Broucke, " A Survey of Methods and Input Data Types for House Price Prediction", *ISPRS Journal*, Vol.12, Issue-5, DOI: 10.3390/ijgi12050200, 2023.
- [4] Dr Mahendra Pawar, "House Price Prediction using Machine Learning", *IRJMETS*, ISSN: 2582- 5208, Vol.5, Issue-3, 2023.
- [5] Ayushi Bhagat, Mayuri Gosavi, "House Price Prediction using Machine Learning", *SSRN*, Elsevier publishers, DOI: 10.2319/ssrn.4413863, 2023.
- [6] Dr Manikandan, "A Literature review on using machine learning algorithm to predict house prices", *IRJASH*, Vol.5, Issue-8, ISSN: 2582-4376, 2023.
- [7] S.S. Yalgudkar, N.V.Dharwadkar, "A literature Survey on Housing Price Prediction", *JCSCM*, DOI: 10.20967/jcscm.2022.03.002, Vol.12, Issue-3, PP: 41- 45, 2022.

- [8] A. Pratap Singh, K. Rastogi, S. Rajpoot, "House Price Prediction Using Machine Learning", 3rd ICACCCN Conference, ISBN: 978-1-6654-3811-7/21, PP: 203 - 206, IEEE Explore, 2021.
- [9] G. Anand Rawool, V. Rogye, S.G. Rane, "House Price Prediction Using Machine Learning", IRE Journal, Vol. 4, Issue-11, ISSN: 2456-8880, PP:29 -33, 2021.
- [10] Quang Truong, Minh Nguyen, Hy Dang, "Housing Price Prediction via Improved Machine Learning Techniques", Procedia Computer Science, ELSEVIER, Science Direct publishers, vol.174, PP: 433-442, 2020.